

Article length and citation outcomes

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Key findings

- A one per cent increase in page length is associated with a 0.56 per cent increase in the number of citations in the top five economics journals.
- A difference-in-difference approach exploiting differential changes in article length over time across top journals also confirms a statistically significant relationship between increased article length and citations.
- A small survey of economists suggests that this effect may be the result of longer articles containing both theory and empirical elements.

What we knew

- Citation counts are significantly higher for longer papers in economics (Card and DellaVigna; 2013).
- The positive association between article length and citations is also found in medicine (Falagas, Zarkali, Karageorgopoulos, Bardakas and Mavros; 2013) and ecology (Fox, Paine and Sauterey; 2016).
- In a meta-analysis of research on the correlation between paper length and citations covering 18 studies from a wide range of research domains including the social sciences, Xie, Gong, Cheng and Ke (2019) find a correlation of 0.3 between citation counts and article length.

What we do

- We investigate whether the length of an article has an effect on the number of citations received by that article.
- Specifically, we examined articles published in the top-five general interest economics journals between 2010 and 2014 combined with citation count data from Google Scholar.
- In our empirical models, we control for a range of factors that can affect citations, including author quality.
- We also conducted a survey of economists at the Australian National University (ANU) to gain additional insight about any consideration they might give to article length in choosing which papers to cite.

What we know now

- Article length, even after controlling for author quality, has a positive relationship with the number of citations. While neither of our approaches is able to identify a causal impact of article length on citation numbers, our estimates provide improved evidence for this relationship in top economics journals.
- Survey responses confirmed that researchers were not aware of article length in choosing which papers to cite, nor did they think that article length, per se, changed the likelihood that they would cite a paper.

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- Survey responses, however, revealed that ANU economists did believe that longer articles are usually comprehensive and focus both on theory and empirical issues.

What this means for academics

- If additional pages are of equally high quality to average pages, then longer articles suggest more breadth and depth of high-quality analysis.
- Lengthy but high-quality papers may better communicate key messages to the profession and receive more citations.

Where to now

- It may be worthwhile to conduct a more extensive survey of researchers in different disciplines (including economics) to learn about preferences for article length. The survey responses are likely to help in revealing how to write papers that can effectively communicate key messages and attract more citations.
- It would be interesting to empirically investigate the association between article length and citations in papers published in A* and A journals in the Journal Quality List of Australian Business Deans Council (ABDC). The analysis can be conducted for multiple disciplines.

More information

- Get the
 - Full working paper
 - Published version [Requires subscription]
- We would welcome the opportunity to present our research to your team and to discuss potential joint research projects on related or similar topics.
- Contact us at robert.breunig@anu.edu.au or s.a.hasan@massey.ac.nz

References

- Card, D. and DellaVigna, S. (2013). Nine facts about top journals in economics, *Journal of Economic Literature* **51**(1): 144–161.
- Falagas, M. E., Zarkali, A., Karageorgopoulos, D. E., Bardakas, V. and Mavros, M. N. (2013). The impact of article length on the number of future citations: a bibliometric analysis of general medicine journals, *PLoS One* **8**(2): e49476.
- Fox, C. W., Paine, C. T. and Sauterey, B. (2016). Citations increase with manuscript length, author number, and references cited in ecology journals, *Ecology and Evolution* **6**(21): 7717–7726.
- Xie, J., Gong, K., Cheng, Y. and Ke, Q. (2019). The correlation between paper length and citations: a meta-analysis, *Scientometrics* **118**(3): 763–786.